

OPTIMIZING BUCK CONVERTER MANAGEMENT THROUGH BASIC MICROCONTROLLER APPLICATION

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Abstract. Modern embedded systems with budget-friendly components face challenges in implementing power switching converters, primarily due to frequency constraints and precision limitations in controlling variable duty cycles for power management. This research explores potential solutions through specialized hardware components to address these restrictions, while investigating the feasibility of multitasking capabilities in microcontrollers - specifically their ability to simultaneously manage power supply control and execute additional low-computational tasks.

Keywords: stepdown converter, computerized control, embedded processor, binary fraction, oscillatory behavior, pulse width modulation

INTRODUCTION

Embedded systems in basic applications often perform dual functions: managing control operations while simultaneously generating alternate voltage outputs, with energy efficiency being crucial for battery-powered devices. Despite using simple architectures, these processors frequently have excess computational capacity during idle periods. This spare processing power creates an opportunity for concurrent execution of power conversion and control functions. To determine the viability of this dual-functionality approach, we developed and tested an experimental system. Our investigation focused on measuring both the limitations of microcontroller-based power regulation and its computational requirements. This research paper is structured in the following manner:

Section II details our experimental setup

Section III examines fundamental switching converter parameters and explains our design methodology

Section IV presents measurement outcomes

Section V concludes with findings and proposes future research directions

THE EXPERIMENTAL TESTBENCH

The experimental setup consists of two primary components: a Digital Controller interfacing with a Power Stage through a Digital Pulse Width Modulator (DPWM).

Digital Controller Specifications

The system utilizes an Arduino Uno board, selected for its educational value in power electronics instruction. This platform features:

Core Components

ATmega328P processor operating at 16 MHz

Instruction execution time of 0.1 microseconds

10-bit Analog to Digital Converter (ADC)

Reference voltage of 5V

Configurable timer unit for DPWM functionality

The setup demonstrates a practical implementation using basic hardware, with the ATmega328P's timer unit serving as the DPWM interface between the digital control system and power stage. The choice of Arduino Uno represents a deliberate selection of an entry-level microcontroller to validate the feasibility of the control approach.

Fig.1 -The experimental testbench

The Power Stage

The system employs a synchronous buck power converter with these key specifications:

Core Components

Two power switches controlled by non-overlapping DPWM outputs

Filter components: inductor ($L = 100 \text{ mH}$) and capacitor ($C = 220 \text{ mF}$)

Capacitor's parasitic series resistance: $90 \text{ m}\Omega$

Operating Parameters

Resonant frequency: approximately 1 kHz

Input voltage range: 10V to 18V

Output voltage range: 2V to 10V

Maximum output current: 2A

Test load resistance: 100Ω

Voltage Management

The design incorporates a voltage scaling system where the output voltage is reduced by a factor K . This scaling ensures the ADC input voltage remains below its reference threshold, even in scenarios where the output voltage equals the input voltage (when the upper switch maintains a closed position).

Design and Operation Principles

A switching buck converter operates on a fundamental principle: the DPWM generates a square wave with duty cycle D that controls power switch operations, converting input voltage V_{in} through an LC filter to produce output voltage V_o . When the square wave frequency significantly exceeds the filter's cutoff frequency, the output voltage maintains near-constant stability, following the relationship:

$$V_o = D \cdot V_{in} \quad (1)$$

The time period of this variable duty cycle square wave defines the switching cycle.

The digital controller's compensator performs two key functions:

Compares ADC input against a digital reference that determines output voltage

Calculates duty cycle D based on the resulting error signal

This compensator operates in periodic control cycles. While integrated controllers typically synchronize switching and control cycles, implementation constraints may result in a control frequency that doesn't exceed the switching frequency:

$$f_{control} \leq f_{sw} \quad (2)$$

The system's performance evaluation focuses on two primary parameters: output regulation and output noise. These factors guide the experimental design choices and implementation strategy.

Output Regulation Characteristics

Output regulation (OR) measures the maximum deviation of DC output voltage from its nominal value and comprises two elements:

Line regulation: accounts for input load fluctuations

Load regulation: reflects load variation effects

The system's output regulation accuracy primarily depends on the ADC precision (NADC), which determines the smallest detectable output voltage change. This relationship is expressed as:

$$OR = V_{ADC} \cdot K \cdot 2^{-NADC} \quad (3)$$

The precision of output regulation exhibits an inverse relationship with the ADC bit count (NADC). To achieve high precision in output voltage control, the system requires an ADC with a higher bit count, as this reduces the minimum detectable voltage variation.

Output Noise Components

The DC output voltage contains AC noise elements arising from two primary sources:

Component parasitic parameters

Digital controller quantization effects (DPWM and ADC)

These manifest as two main noise types: Ripple noise (ΔV) and Limit Cycle (LC) noise

Ripple Noise Characteristics

Ripple noise emerges from the inductor current's AC component interacting with the power stage's output capacitor. This interaction, combined with the capacitor's non-zero Equivalent Series Resistance (ESR), creates a voltage fluctuation at the switching frequency f_{sw} . The peak ripple voltage follows the relationship:

$$\Delta V = \Delta I \cdot ESR = \frac{V_{in} D(1-D)}{L \cdot f_{sw}} ESR \quad (4)$$

Key characteristics of ripple noise:

Reaches maximum amplitude when duty cycle (D) equals 0.5

Exhibits inverse relationship with switching frequency

Can be minimized by increasing switching frequency while maintaining constant inductance

The noise amplitude's dependence on switching frequency provides a crucial design consideration for output voltage regulation.

Limit Cycle Noise Analysis

Limit Cycle (LC) noise occurs due to DPWM quantization, where duty cycle D values are limited to $2^{N_{PWM}}$ discrete levels, with N_{PWM} representing the modulator control bits. The voltage differential between consecutive duty cycles is expressed as:

$$\Delta V_i = V_{in} 2^{-N_{PWM}} \quad (5)$$

When the target voltage falls between quantized output levels, the output oscillates between adjacent levels V_{oi} and V_{oi+1} as the controller attempts to maintain the target voltage.

Oscillation Characteristics

The oscillation frequency matches either the control frequency or its subharmonic, influenced by multiple factors:

- Filter cutoff frequency
- Controller parameters
- Load conditions
- Ripple voltage amplitude
- Noise Reduction Strategies

While dithering techniques can shift noise components to higher frequencies for filtering, they become ineffective when control frequency approaches filter cutoff frequency. An alternative approach involves preventing oscillation between output levels by ensuring the ADC quantization bin which exceeds the PWM's Least Significant Bit (LSB):

$$q_{ADC} > q_{PWM} \quad (6)$$

This relationship, considering system parameters, expands to:

$$\frac{V_{REF}}{2^{N_{ADC}}} > \frac{V_{inMAX}}{2^{N_{PWM}}} \quad (7)$$

When

$$V_R = V_{inMAX}$$

the condition simplifies to:

$$N_{PWM} > N_{ADC} \quad (8)$$

This solution presents a trade-off: reducing ADC bits which eliminates limit cycle noise but compromises output regulation precision.

Implementation Strategy

Hardware constraints necessitate careful design choices for microcontroller-based converters. A pure software DPWM implementation using nested counter loops with NPWM=8 would demand thousands of instructions per switching cycle, resulting in approximately 4 kHz switching frequencies and producing unacceptable ripple noise around 1V. Such implementation would also consume all CPU resources.

Hardware Solution

The ATmega328P's dedicated timer/counter unit provides an efficient DPWM solution with:

- Two programmable thresholds controlling output pin transitions
- First threshold determines duty cycle
- Second threshold sets switching frequency and triggers counter reset
- Direct 16 MHz clock input capability

Operating Parameters

The selected configuration balances NPWM and switching frequency:

- NPWM = 8 bits
- fsw = 64kHz
- Maximum ripple noise: 70mV under worst conditions

Control System

The software implements a Proportional-Integrative (PI) compensator with these characteristics:

- Control cycle duration: ~200 μs
- ADC conversion time: 100 μs

Maximum theoretical control frequency: 5 kHz

Actual implemented control frequency: 1 kHz via timer interrupt

CPU utilization: 20% for control tasks

Available CPU time for other tasks: 80%

This implementation acknowledges that limit cycle noise cannot be effectively filtered by the 1 kHz output filter when control frequency falls below 5 kHz.

Fig. 2- Limit cycle noise

Measurement Methodology

Two measurement sets were conducted:

Initial measurements without limit cycle restrictions

Secondary measurements implementing equation of 6 conditions

Testing parameters included:

Output voltage range: 2V to 9V

Input voltage range: 10V to 18V (1V increments)

Ripple Voltage Analysis

The measured ripple voltage showed lower than predicted values, with maximum peak-to-peak measurements at $V_{in}=18V$ and $V_{out}=9V$. Voltage spike observations were attributed to probe-gate switch driver coupling effects. The reduced ripple magnitude likely results from lower capacitor parasitic resistance.

Limit Cycle Noise Characteristics

LC noise manifested distinctly, with a pattern of:

4 cycles at upper duty cycle value

24 cycles at lower duty cycle value

The noise appeared selectively, occurring only when input-output voltage combinations caused ADC output changes from single duty cycle variations.

Performance Analysis

Standard Configuration

Output voltage demonstrated satisfactory line regulation

Error margins remained within acceptable ranges for typical applications

Modified Controller Results Implementation of LC noise cancellation (per equation 8) through ADC precision reduction resulted in:

Increased error magnitude (4-5 times larger than standard configuration)
 Modified output voltage behavior across input voltage range
 The measurements confirm the theoretical trade-off between limit cycle noise elimination and output regulation precision.

Fig. 3 Maximum ripple at switching

$V_{in} \backslash V_{out}$	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	120
3	0	0	0	0	80	0	0	0	130
4	0	0	0	70	0	0	0	0	150
5	0	60	0	70	0	0	0	0	150
6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0
7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	0	90	100	0
9	0	0	0	0	70	0	90	0	0

Fig. 4. LC noise (in mV) for all V_{in} and V_{out} combinations

V_{out}	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
e	180	200	200	200	210	200	200	200

Fig.5 – Output error e in mV for a LC free setting

Fig.6. V_{out} as a function of V_{in} for a non-LC free setting

V. CONCLUSIONS AND DEVELOPMENTS

This investigation demonstrates the successful implementation of a buck converter controller utilizing a conventional low-performance microcontroller. Through strategic utilization of the processor's hardware capabilities, efficient power conversion was achieved, albeit with inherent optimization constraints due to processor limitations. The experimental results indicate a significant trade-off in practical applications: systems must balance between enhanced DC output precision accompanied by elevated limit cycle noise, or reduced output precision with diminished noise characteristics. This compromise represents a fundamental design consideration for implementation-specific requirements. Further research directions should address the dynamic characteristics of the converter, particularly focusing on:

- Response characteristics to input voltage fluctuations
- Load transient behavior
- System stability under varying conditions

These aspects remain unexplored in the current study due to instrumentation limitations, necessitating more sophisticated measurement apparatus for comprehensive analysis. Such investigation would provide valuable insights into the complete operational envelope of the proposed implementation.

The findings herein establish a foundation for future optimization strategies in low-cost microcontroller-based power conversion systems, while acknowledging the inherent performance boundaries of such implementations.

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